

An Experimental and Analytical Evaluation of Bi-Element Composite Targets

Nevin L. Rupert,* Evan Gellert, and Stephen D. Pattie
Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory
Ship Structures and Materials Division
P.O. Box 4331
Melbourne, Victoria 3001
Australia

ABSTRACT

Advanced fiber composite laminates can offer significant strength and stiffness improvements over conventional metals on a weight-to-weight basis. With the current interest in composite armored vehicles, understanding the composite penetration process and how it relates to laminated composites becomes very important. This work found that a one-dimensional code may be successful as a lower cost replacement for two-dimensional and axisymmetric two-dimensional hydrocode models to describe the penetration.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber composite laminates can offer significant strength and stiffness improvements over conventional metals on a weight-to-weight basis. Thus there is widespread use of such materials in secondary aerospace components and some primary structural applications. Such successful applications in aerospace components have generated interest in the development of composite armors for lightweight vehicles in several countries. Since armored vehicles must survive ballistic attack, understanding the penetration process and how it relates to laminated composites becomes very important. The anisotropic nature of laminated composites, along with additional defeat mechanisms, such as unsymmetrical erosion, not found in conventional isotropic armor materials, complicates the modeling of the penetration process. This work explores the use of a one-dimensional model as a lower cost replacement for the two-dimensional and axisymmetric two-dimensional hydrocode models.

*From 28 July to 18 November 1994, the author was assigned as an exchange scientist to the Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, Ship Structures and Materials Division, from the U. S. Army Research Laboratory, AMSRL-WT-TA, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD 21005-5066, USA.

EXPERIMENTAL

PENETRATOR

The blunted tungsten alloy penetrator used in this study is illustrated in Fig. 1. The blunted core was produced from a 0.50-cal. sabot light-armor penetrator (SLAP) manufactured by Winchester Repeating Arms Company. The penetrator core had a diameter of 7.72 mm, a final length of 25.05 ± 0.03 mm, and a mass of 23.13 ± 0.01 g. To achieve the necessary flat-fronted cylindrical shape, the projectile tip was removed by grinding, which does not change the material properties. Analysis of the tungsten penetrator alloy indicated 93% W, 2.1% Fe, and 4.9% Ni. Nominal material properties measured for these penetrators are as follows: density - 17.73 g/cm^3 , hardness (HV30) - 500. A strength of 1.742 GPa was estimated from the hardness of the penetrator core [1]. A second strength value of 1.51 GPa was acquired from two additional sources on a similar tungsten alloy, Johnson and Cook [2], and from Cimpoeru and Woodward [3]. The penetrators were fired from a 0.50-cal. M2HB machine gun with a 1,143-mm-long barrel at an average muzzle velocity of $1,120 \pm 10$ m/s. The gun muzzle was positioned 130 ± 2 mm in front of the target. At this velocity, the penetrator had a spin rate between 2,900 and 3,000 rps.

Figure 1. The 0.50-cal. SLAP (left) and a blunted core (right).

TARGET DESCRIPTIONS

Four basic targets were tested. The first was a clamped stack of four 38-mm 5083-H113 aluminum plates. Properties attributed to these aluminum plates are as follows: density - 2.73 g/cm^3 , yield strength - 230 MPa, Young's modulus - 72.4 GPa, plasticity modulus - 0.55 GPa, and speed of sound - 5,240 m/s. A static ultimate strength of 452 MPa was measured for the aluminum [4]. The other targets were bi-element with the second (backing) element comprising the aluminum stack described above.

The second target was a titanium/aluminum bi-element target. This target was used as a calibration check on the modeling of the penetrator. The first element in this target consisted of a single 23-mm-thick plate of titanium (Ti-6Al-4V) adhesively bonded to the first plate of the second element. The target plates were mechanically clamped prior to testing. Titanium properties used in the modeling of this target are as follows [5,6]: density - 4.45 g/cm^3 , nominal strength - 930 MPa, yield strength - 862 MPa, Young's modulus - 113.8 GPa, plasticity modulus - 1.9 GPa, and speed of sound - 6,070 m/s.

The last two targets consisted of glass fabric reinforced plastic (GRP)/aluminum bi-element targets where the GRP section was of equivalent areal density to the titanium applique. The GRP used either S2-glass or E-glass fabric. Fabrication of the GRP involved a staged process of lamination and cure of glass fabric with DERAKANE 411-45 vinylester resin until the requisite areal density of target was achieved. At each stage of the lamination process, no more than 14 plies were added. The laminate was vacuum bagged at 85 kPa at $25^\circ\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hr at each stage. The completed laminates were then postcured at 90°C for 2 hr. The GRP laminates were then adhesively bonded to the first plate of the second element (four

38-mm 5083-H113 plates). The entire target was then mechanically clamped prior to testing. Properties in the modeling for the two composites are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Composite Geometric and Engineering Parameters

Parameters	Values	
	S2-Glass	E-Glass
Through-Axis Young's Modulus, E (GPa)	9.3	8.9
Through-Axis Compressive Strength, S_t (MPa)	620	355
Density (g/cm^3)	1.78	1.87
Average Ply Thickness (mm)	0.57	0.53
Reinforcement (weight-percent)	76.8	84.8
Reinforcement Density (g/cm^3)	2.49	2.55
Reinforcement Modulus (GPa)	86.8	72.4
Reinforcement Poisson's Ratio	0.22	0.22
Matrix (weight-percent)	23.2	15.2
Matrix Density (g/cm^3)	1.12	1.12
Matrix Modulus (GPa)	3.45	3.45
Matrix Poisson's Ratio	0.35	0.35

BALLISTIC RESULTS

Penetration depths into aluminum and residual lengths for the 25-mm-long blunted SLAP are given in Table 2. Depths were measured normal to the surface of the first aluminum plate, using probes and x-ray technologies. For four cases, the targets were sectioned and the actual depths were measured. For two of these, the depth was taken as the length of the curve path created by the penetrator (see Fig. 3). The length of the curved path is given in parentheses. Residual penetrator lengths were measured for only the cases marked with an asterisk (*).

Table 2. Penetration Depth in Aluminum Backing Element and Residual Penetrator Lengths

Targets	Residual Penetration Depth into 5083-H113 Aluminum (mm)	Residual Penetrator Length (mm)
5083-H113 Aluminum	95, 85, 85*	15.6
Titanium/Aluminum	21.0,* 20.5	10.6
E-Glass Fabric Composite/Aluminum	46.0 (50.7),* 34.5	17.0
S2-Glass Fabric Composite/Aluminum	23.5, 42.0 (50.6)*	18.7

*Residual penetrator length was measured from this test.

OBSERVATIONS

Sectioning of the monolithic aluminum target indicated that no rotational effects or nonsymmetrical erosion of the penetrator tip for the blunted and spinning SLAP rounds had occurred. Fig. 2 illustrates the same lack of rotational effects with the titanium/aluminum bi-element target. However, Fig. 3 indicates that an additional interaction between the target and the penetrator had taken place. An unsymmetrical erosion of the penetrator nose and a curving of the penetrator path were observed in each composite bi-element target. The curvatures of the penetration path were random relative to the composite's axes of symmetry. Cratering was observed in all targets. For the composite targets, the cratering seemed to be more exaggerated. The glass fibers outside the cratered region appeared to be sheared and showed no sign of distortion that generally would be associated with material flow in metallic targets. It should be noted that Fig. 3 is typical of all the composite bi-element targets tested.

Figure 2. Sectioned titanium/aluminum bi-element target

Figure 3. Sectioned woven E-glass composite/aluminum bi-element target

Additional tests with identical targets and nonspinning blunted 0.50-cal. SLAP penetrators are to be conducted by the Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory. This work is proposed to determine whether spin-stabilization affects the erosion of the penetrator and the curving path of the penetrator.

MODELING

To model the penetration of the composite bi-element targets, two different models were used. The first model, based on the nonsteady penetration theory by Grace, deals with target penetration during the initial phase, when the penetrator undergoes erosion [7]. The second treats target penetration during a subsequent phase where the rod remains rigid. The terms used to differentiate the two processes are "eroding-body" penetration, and "rigid-body" penetration, respectively [6].

The nonsteady penetration development of Grace was used to analyze the eroding-body penetration [7], with its applications to bi-element targets [5,8]. Impact conditions used are rod impact velocity v_s , initial rod length ℓ_0 , and first element thickness a_0 . \mathcal{F}_c is the correction for higher penetration efficiencies based on length-to-diameter ratio as determined from the data of Hohler and Stilp [9]. The composite first element is treated as a monolithic material with orthotropic properties in the penetration model [10]. The second element is an isotropic semi-infinite metal. It is assumed that the total penetration P_t is the sum of penetration through each element. This gives

$$P_t = \mathcal{F}_c \int_{\ell_0}^{\ell_1} \left(\frac{u}{v-u} \right)_1 dl + P_{RB1} + \mathcal{F}_c \int_{\ell_1}^{\ell_2} \left(\frac{u}{v-u} \right)_2 dl + P_{RB2}, \quad (1)$$

where $[u / (v - u)]_1$ and $[u / (v - u)]_2$ are respective velocities for the two elements within the eroding-body phase, and P_{RB1} and P_{RB2} are the subsequent rigid-body penetration within the two elements. The first integral and P_{RB1} are equal to a_0 , or

$$a_0 = \mathcal{F}_c \int_{\ell_0}^{\ell_1} \left(\frac{u}{v-u} \right)_1 dl + P_{RB1}. \quad (2)$$

However, it is necessary to calculate the penetration through the first element to determine penetrator length ℓ_1 , v_2 , and erosion rates $[u / (v - u)]_2$ to be used in the second integral. It should be noted that when rigid-body penetration is involved, the limits ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 are determined when rod erosion stops. This results in the condition where $(v - u)_1$ or $(v - u)_2$ equals zero, which are given in the previous work [7] or by a cutoff velocity [6]. When solving Eqn (2), penetration into the first element as given by the first integral is calculated stepwise as if the element were semi-infinite. The process continues up to the point where the depth of penetration reaches a_0 or rod erosion stops. This provides the starting conditions v_{c0} and ℓ_1 for the start of P_{RB1} if rod erosion stops, or v_1 , u_1 , and ℓ_1 , for the second integral if the depth of a_0 is reached before rod erosion stops.

Penetration into the first element was calculated using previous methods [5] which account for the shock transient due to impact at the target front surface. Beyond the penetration contribution given by the first integral, P_{RB1} must be calculated separately to determine v_2 . For present purposes, P_{RB1} is calculated using an Alekseevskii/Tate penetration algorithm for rigid-body penetration, but is modified here to take into account the finite extent of the first element. The modified equation has the following form:

$$P_{RB1} = \frac{\rho_p \ell_1}{2k_t \rho_1} \left[1 + \frac{k_t \rho_1 (v_{co}^2 - v_1^2)}{H} \right], \quad (3)$$

where v_1 is the rod velocity when it reaches the interface.

The Alekseevskii formulation treats k_t as a shape factor. Tate takes the value for k_t to be 0.5, corresponding to the value which appears in the Bernoulli equation. v_{co} is the critical velocity at which rod erosion stops. The value of v_{co} is determined when the pressure on the nose of the penetrator drops below the stress required for rod erosion, P_c . The total stress on the rod due to its flow into the target is the sum of the dynamic pressure due to its velocity plus the strength of the target, or

$$P_c = \frac{1}{2} \rho_t v_{co}^2 + S_t. \quad (4)$$

The target resistance pressure H is calculated using Goodier's expanding spherical cavity analysis [11]. Accordingly, the target resistance is as follows:

$$H = \frac{2Y_{ys}}{3} \left[1 + \ln \left(\frac{2E}{3Y_{ys}} \right) \right] + \frac{2\pi^2}{27} E_t, \quad (5)$$

where Y_{ys} is the target yield strength, E is Young's modulus, and E_t is the slope from the yield point to the ultimate strength point, assuming a bilinear stress-strain curve. However, for the composite GRP elements, Y_{ys} is taken to be the composite's ultimate strength in the direction of the penetrator's path, E is Young's modulus in the direction of the penetrator path, and E_t is zero [10].

It is possible that the rigid rod coming from the first element could begin eroding again as the second element is encountered. The second integral is calculated stepwise up to the point where the rod stops eroding. This provides the penetration depth P_2 into the second element during the eroding phase, with rod length ℓ_2 and v_3 as starting conditions for the rigid-body penetration portion in the second element. Since the backing target is semi-infinite, P_{RB2} is determined using the Alekseevskii/Tate penetration algorithm for rigid-body penetration, in its original form, as presented by Zook et al. [12] and takes the following form:

$$P_{RB2} = \frac{\rho_p \ell_1}{2k_t \rho_1} \left[1 + \frac{k_t \rho_1 v_3^2}{H} \right], \quad (6)$$

where k_t is 0.5 and H is calculated using Eqn (5).

The composite failure criteria used in one-dimensional penetration can be implemented in two ways, either as a one-dimensional strain or as a one-dimensional stress along the penetrator path. The one-dimensional strain assumption would be expected to provide a greater total energy dissipation, which should result in a lower penetration depth and/or smaller hole diameter. The limited characterization of the composites enabled only the one-dimensional stress criterion to be used in the analysis presented here, using the compressive strength from Table 1. This appears to provide reasonable results for the eroding-body penetration as seen by comparing residual penetrator lengths from Tables 2 and 3. In view of the large reductions in penetrator length, and the nonhomogeneous structure of the GRP elements in the targets, the agreement between experimental and computed residual lengths is assessed to be good,

and indicates that the "eroding-body" model is capable of describing this penetration process. Future work should investigate both one-dimensional stress and one-dimensional strain to determine the most suitable failure model.

Table 3. Computational Results

Targets	For Penetrator Strength of 1.742 GPa		For Penetrator Strength of 1.510 GPa	
	Residual Penetration Depth (mm)	Residual Penetrator Length (mm)	Residual Penetration Depth (mm)	Residual Penetrator Length (mm)
Aluminum	103.5	18.9	92.0	15.6
Titanium/Aluminum	27.8	13.7	24.0	12.9
E-Glass Fabric Composite/Aluminum	85.2	18.6	58.0	15.5
S2-Glass Fabric Composite/Aluminum	96.8	16.9	74.9	14.5

The presence of the curved penetration path within the aluminum element defines the actual penetration process as a three-dimensional problem. If hydrocodes are to be used for composite armors with or without spinning penetrators, full three-dimensional models are required to address the nonsymmetrical erosion of the tip and changes in penetration direction. Monte-Carlo techniques may be an option to address the effect of stacking offsets for the plies, the homogeneity of the composite, and hit locations relative to the weave of the reinforcement. Trends, not actual depth of penetration estimates, can be calculated using one-dimensional, two-dimensional, or axisymmetrical models because of the curvature in the penetration paths. The bases for artificially introducing the rotational off-axis effects resulting from the penetration of a composite structure by a rotating projectile will have to be determined after the following questions are answered: Is the nonsymmetrical erosion of the penetrator introducing a moment about the penetrator center of mass during "rigid-body" penetration causing it to turn in the aluminum? Is the uneven loading of the penetrator tip from the composite nonhomogeneity destabilizing the spinning penetrator causing it to turn? Is the spin stabilization of the penetration keeping the penetrator from turning sooner?

SUMMARY

The anisotropic nature of laminated composites, along with additional defeat mechanisms not found in conventional isotropic armor materials, complicates the modeling of the penetration process. The curved penetration path observed in the aluminum backing target implies that three-dimensional effects are present. Since two-dimensional codes cannot treat off-axis effects, they may offer little advantage over a one-dimensional technique. As such, the one-dimensional model may be adequate as a lower cost replacement for the two-dimensional and axisymmetrical two-dimensional hydrocode models.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge the assistance of Mr. Jim Dimas in carrying out the ballistic test and target preparation.

REFERENCES

1. D. Tabor, *The Hardness of Metals*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1951.
2. G. R. Johnson, and W. H. Cook, Fracture characteristics of three metals subjected to various strains, strain rates, temperatures and pressures. *Engng. Frac. Mech.* **21**, 31–48 (1985).
3. S. J. Cimpoeru and R. L. Woodward, High strain rate properties of three liquid phase sintered tungsten alloys. *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, **9**, 187–191 (1990).
4. R. L. Woodward, Unpublished data (1994).
5. F. I. Grace, and N. L. Rupert, Mechanisms for ceramic/metal, semi-infinite, bi-element target response to ballistic impact. TB-16, *Ball. '93, 14th Int. Symp.*, **2**, 361–370, Quebec City, Quebec, Canada (1993).
6. N. L. Rupert and F. I. Grace, Penetration of long rods into titanium/aluminum, bi-element targets. *Proceedings of the Fifth Annual TACOM Combat Vehicle Survivability Symposium, Volume I - Unclassified Session Papers*, 427–436, Monterey, California, (1994).
7. F. I. Grace, Non-steady penetration of long rods into semi-infinite targets. *Int. J. Impact Engng.* **14**, 303–314 (1993).
8. N. L. Rupert and F. I. Grace, Penetration of long rods into semi-infinite, bi-element targets. TB-27, *Ballistic '93, 14th International Symposium*, **2**, 469–478, Quebec City, Quebec, Canada (1993).
9. V. Hohler and A. J. Stilp, Influence of the length-to-diameter ratio in the range from 1 to 32 on the penetration performance of rod projectiles. *Proc. 8th Int. Symp. Ball.* IB-13-IB-19, Orlando, Florida, USA (1984).
10. N. L. Rupert, Ply orientation effects on the penetration of fiber-reinforced composite materials. *Ball. '95, 15th Int. Symp.*, Jerusalem, Israel (to be published).
11. J. N. Goodier, On the mechanics of indentation and cratering in solid targets of strain-hardening metal by impact of hard and soft spheres. *Proc. 7th Hyp.-Vel. Imp. Symp.*, Vol. III - Theory. 215–259, Orlando, FL (1965).
12. J. A. Zook, K. Frank, and G. F. Silsby, Terminal ballistic test and analysis guidelines for penetration mechanics branch. BRL-MR-390, U. S. Army Ballistic Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD (1992).